

MANUFACTURING AN IOT DEVICE FOR AUTOMATIC CONTROL OF TOTAL DISSOLVED SOLIDS OF NUTRIENT CONCENTRATION FOR PLANTS ON AEROPONIC, HYDROPONIC SYSTEMS

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Received Date: 07/9/2022; Revised Date: 20/10/2022; Accepted for Publication: 21/10/2022

SUMMARY

Controlling TDS (Total Dissolved Solids) in aeroponic and hydroponic systems is very important for plant growth. Due to the reflux of the nutrient solution after passing through the tube system containing the medium, the concentration of nutrients decreases. Currently, measuring nutrient concentration and adding nutrients to the solution is manually done by farmers. Therefore, we manufactured an IoT (Internet of Things) device with acceptable accuracy to control nutrient concentration. In testing, the TDS sensor has a relative error of $\sim 1.2\%$. The IoT device can automatically turn on the pump to provide more nutrients when its TDS is below the TDS threshold and turn off the pump when the concentration has reached the threshold. With our system, users can directly enter the TDS threshold using the matrix keypad or via the Blynk smart-phone application.

Keywords: *IoT, nutrient concentration, aeroponic and hydroponic systems, TDS.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam is a country with a long-standing development in agriculture. However, climate change leads to natural disasters, constant floods which effect on agricultural production. In addition, the traditional methods of production are now not highly effective. Therefore, farmers try to find new technologies for agriculture. The technologies that are used quite a lot in agriculture are aeroponics and hydroponics in greenhouses.

Hydroponics is a form of growing plants in solution without soil. It is the system of agricultural cultivation using water growing media including a nutrient solution. Growing plants by the hydroponic method has the following advantages: It is possible to choose places where the soil is barren, infertile or agricultural land interspersed in residential areas with a small area; if growing hydroponic vegetables is in greenhouses, environmental conditions can be controlled, so it is possible to increase the number of crops per year; plants grow and develop in suitable conditions, so yields and quality of product are high; plants are grown in closed hydroponic troughs, which limits water infiltration and loss, thus saving water for irrigation (Suseno et al., 2019; Velazquez-Gonzalez et al., 2022). With aeroponics, the plants are grown in a medium and their roots are suspended in the air, provided with water and nutrients by misting. Misting is usually done every few minutes, so the plants have enough nutrients

and water and always have air to breathe. Plants need macronutrients and trace elements for their best growth and development. The development of aeroponics vegetables does not require pesticides or growth drugs, which helps farmers to have a source of clean vegetables and have stable markets (Gopinath et al., 2017).

Nutrients in hydroponics and aeroponics are usually measured as total dissolved solids (TDS). TDS is one of the indicators used to test the quality of water, the content of all organic and inorganic substances contained in a liquid (TDS unit: mg/l (minigrams/liter) or ppm (part/million)). TDS is not considered an indicator of contamination, it is a composite indicator of the presence of chemical compounds. TDS is measured with a dedicated sensor. The TDS sensor is basically an electrical charge (EC) sensor whereby two electrodes are inserted into the water and used to measure the charge. The result is analyzed by the TDS sensor and converted into ppm values. If the water contains no soluble and pure material, it will not conductive materials. Hence the ppm value is 0. Conversely, if the water is filled with solutes, it will be conductive. In this case, the ppm values obtained will be proportional to the number of dissolved solids. This is because all dissolved solids have an electrical charge, allowing charge transfer between electrodes (Dfrobot, 2020; Maheshwari and Chakraborty, 2021). Nutrients are provided with TDS values which are appropriate

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to each plant type and growth stage. For example, the ideal TDS levels for mustard greens, basil, bok choy, lettuce,... are 60-1200 ppm, 800-1100 ppm, 750-1250 ppm, 400-600 ppm ...respectively (ZipGrow, 2021).

The fourth stage of the agricultural sector's revolution, known as Agriculture 4.0, is brought by current advancements in communication technologies like Cloud Computing and the Internet of Things (IoTs) combining with advanced technologies like Computational Intelligence, Robotics, Big Data, etc (Konstantinos et al. 2020). Susanti et al. (2022) also constructed an IoT device using the NodeMCU esp8266 chip and a TDS probe that can send data to a smartphone. This IoT device is for water quality testing in fish farming. Suseno et al. (2019) built a TDS hydroponic nutrient as a remote monitor. This device uses a TDS sensor, an Arduino DUE chip, an esp8266 WiFi module, and motors. TDS data is uploaded to the website of the Thingspeak server, which is convenient for monitoring the change of nutrient concentration.

In short, controlling nutrient concentration is very important for plant growth. Due to the reflux of the nutrient solution after passing through the tube system containing the medium, the concentration of nutrients decreases. Currently, monitoring nutrient concentration and adding nutrition to the solution are done manually by famers. Therefore, we manufactured an equipment using IoT platform that can automatically monitor and control nutrient concentration for plants in aeroponic and hydroponic systems to save time and production costs for farmers.

2. RESEARCH CONTENTS, METHODS NAND MATERIALS

2.1. Research contents

- Overview of the characteristics of the hydroponic and aeroponic systems, researching and manufacturing the IoT device for growing plants in greenhouses.

- Manufacturing the IoT device to control nutrient concentrations for aeroponics and hydroponics systems.

- Calibrating the IoT device.

- Designing smartphone application to remotely control by a smartphone.

- Evaluating its accuracy and stability.

2.2. Research methods

- * Theoretical research methods

- Analyzing and synthesizing documents

to learn about the models of aeroponic and hydroponic systems.

- Learning the application of IoTs in smart agriculture

- Learning the principles of microcontrollers, sensors, electronic components, and the Arduino programming language.

- * Experimental method

- Designing the circuit board, assemble control circuit and actuator for pumping nutrient and water

- Calibrating the sensors

- Testing the IoT device in greenhouse and evaluating product quality.

2.3. Materials

Preparing components and materials (Table 1): a TDS probe with an amplifier, a DS18B20 temperature sensor, a NodeMCU microcontroller, LCD screen, 4 x 4 matrix keyboard, a module 2 relays 5VDC, two booster pumps, two contactors 220V-25A, a T89 power module and a router connected to the internet. There are also waterproof plastic boxes to store the sensor's amplifier circuit and the main control circuit.

Table 1. Table of components and material

No.	Components and material	Quantity
1	TDS probe and amplifier	1
2	Temperature sensor DS18B20	1
3	Arduino ESP8266 NodeMcu CH340 WIFI V3	1
4	LCD display 1602 and I2C converter	1
5	Matrix Keyboard	1
6	Booster pump with filter and 12 VDC power supply	2
7	Cotactor CHINT	2
9	Two chanel relay Module	1
10	T89 power module	1

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Manufacturing and assembling

- Wiring diagrams design

The wiring diagram is shown in Figure 1. The signal wires of the TDS (1) and DS18B20 (2) sensors are connected to pin A0, D0 of the NodeMCU microcontroller (3), respectively. The matrix keyboard is connected to the NodeMCU microcontroller in the following order: pins D1-D4 matche rows R1-R4 of the matrix keyboard (4), and D5-D7 pins correspond to columns C1-C3. The module relay (5) is powered by 5VDC

and its two-input signals are connected to pins D8 and S3 of the NodeMCU microcontroller. The two outputs of the relay module are connected to two CHINT contactors (6). The SDA (Serial data) and SCL (Serial clock) pins of the LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) module (7) connect to the RX (receiving) and TX (transmitting) pins of the microcontroller. The LCD module is powered by 5VDC from the T89 power module (8).

Figure 1. Connection and Wiring diagram
- Assembly and construction

Connect sensors, matrix keyboard, relay module, etc. to the microcontroller according to the diagram in Figure 1. The amplifier board for the TDS sensor and main circuit board including microcontroller, supply power, actuators are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively. They are enclosed in waterproof plastic boxes. The connection diagram of the control circuit board with the contactors and the pumps is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2. Amplifier of sensors and connectors in a plastic box

Figure 3. The circuit board inside the box (a) and completed IoT device (b)

Figure 4. Connection diagram of with contactor and pump (a) and Panel of booster pumps (b)

3.2. Algorithm flowchart design

An algorithm flowchart for controller programming using Arduino language is designed as follows:

Figure 5. Flowchart of algorithm of Arduino program

When the program runs, the sensors will read the initial parameters of the nutrient solution and notify the users on the LCD display and the Blynk application. In addition, on the Blynk application, there will be an emergency stop button so that users can stop the system at any time. When active water is pumped into the medium first, after reaching a certain level, the users can now select the TDS threshold that is suitable for their plants. The system reads TDS values of the environment, and

compares them with the thresholds entered by the users. If the TDS of the nutrient solution is lower than the thresholds, the pump will be activated and inject the core nutrient into the solution until the TDS is greater than or equal to the thresholds.

3.3. Implement of the Blynk application

We install the Blynk application on the Android or IOS system. The Blynk application helps us to control the system via the internet. Users can monitor TDS value of nutrient solution, control water and nutrient pumps remotely.

Use the “LCD” Widget tools to indicate the temperature and TDS. We use a widget named “Slider” so the user can set the TDS threshold. We also created an option menu using the “Menu” widget to choose a nutrient pump or a water pump.

Figure 6. Blynk application interface

3.4. Calibrating the sensor and testing the device

It is necessary to calibrate the sensors because the new circuit causes measurement errors. The TDS sensor connected to the microcontroller and a high-precision industrial meter are used to measure the TDS value of solution simultaneously. Then, we compared the two results of these two devices to find the calibration factor.

Firstly, we use the TDS-3 meter to measure the concentration of impurities and the temperature of the solution in the plastic cup (the value is measured by an industrial meter with an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$). Pure water is used and mixed with pure coffee to measure different TDS values. We gradually increase the concentration of coffee in the solution in the cup. We use the TDS-3 meter and a IoT device manufactured by us to simultaneously measure TDS and temperature values and record the results in Table 2.

Table 2. Voltage and TDS values of calibration

No.	Voltage (V)	TDS (ppm)	
		TDS-3 meter	IoT device
1	0.31	118	118
2	0.58	241	214
3	0.78	336	322
4	0.98	436	384
5	1.16	518	475
6	1.47	640	612
7	1.64	704	700
8	1.76	856	827
9	2.05	956	916
10	2.23	1050	1036
11	2.31	1150	1057
12	2.32	1270	1045
13	2.34	1450	1067
14	2.34	1520	1060
15	2.34	1620	1062
16	2.34	1820	1079
17	2.34	3420	1083

Figure 7. Graph showing the relationship between TDS and voltage

Figure 7 shows that comparison between the two results of the industrial TDS meter and the IoT device. It can be seen that the TDS sensor of the IoT device reaches the saturation threshold at about 1050ppm. From here, it is concluded that the TDS sensor is suitable for implementation in vegetable gardens that need nutrient concentration with maximum TDS of 1050 ppm.

Table 3. The rate of TDS values recorded by TDS-3 meter and IoT device

No.	TDS (ppm)		Rate
	TDS-3 meter	IoT device	
1	118	118	1
2	241	214	1.126
3	336	322	1.043
4	436	384	1.135
5	518	475	1.091
6	640	612	1.046
7	704	700	1.006
8	856	827	1.035
9	956	916	1.043
10	1050	1036	1.014
Average			1.054

Figure 8. Correlation between TDS values measured by IoT device and TDS-3 meter

Figure 8 shows the linear relationship between the two values measured by the industrial TDS-3 meter and the IoT device with the high coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.997$. Thus, in order to calibrate the sensor, we divide the value of the industrial device by the measured value of the IoT device. So, the calibration factor is 1.054. The calibration factor is the multiplier for the script code that reads the TDS values.

3.5. Testing ability of IoT device in the greenhouse

The field study was carried out in the aeroponic vegetable garden of a farmer in Hoa Thang, Buon Ma Thuot, Dak Lak on June 1, 2022 with the aim of testing the working ability of the IoT device. We checked the ability to control nutrient concentration through the smartphone.

Figure 9. Testing IoT device in a greenhouse of a farmer in Hoa Thang, Buon Ma Thuot, Dak Lak

In our testing in the greenhouse, we used a nutrient bucket that is a nutrient solution of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium (NPK) fertilizer. The TDS value of this nutrient is often very large; specifically in the experimental case, the value is 4450 ppm.

Figure 10. Water and nutrient pumps into the final solution bucket

Connect the Blynk application to the system, the system that selects the water through the application injects water in the final nutrient bucket. TDS of this bucket without NPK is 72ppm

After the water in the bucket reaches the required level, we switch the mode to the nutrient pump and enter the TDS threshold. In this case, the TDS value is entered by 1000 ppm.

In principle, if we set up the threshold of the nutrient solution pump. it will stop working when the TDS value reaches 1000 ppm. However, in reality there are many factors that will affect TDS such as swirling water or nutrition. In the progress of our experiment, the input TDS threshold is 1000 ppm, but the actual value obtained after the nutrient pump stopping is 1042 ppm. The relative error is about 4.2%.

Figure 11. Representation of TDS values measured simultaneously by TDS-3 meter and IoT device.

In order to discuss on the accuracy of the IoT device, the formula for calculating the relative error (%) between industrial meter and manufactured device can be used:

$$\frac{|TDS_{TDS-3meter} - TDS_{IoTdevice}|}{TDS_{TDS-3meter}} \times 100$$

Here, we consider the case of the industrial meter showing 1030 ppm. At this time, the manufactured device indicates a value of 1042 ppm.

$$\frac{|1030 - 1042|}{1030} \times 100 \approx 1,2\%$$

From above results, it can be seen that the relative error is quite low. From Figure 11, it can be seen that the TDS values simultaneously measured by industrial meter and manufactured device are quite close to each other. From here, the IoT device can be judged with acceptable accuracy. The IoT device can measure nutrient concentrations up to 1050 ppm and can apply for nutrient mixing and control in aeroponics and hydroponics for plants such as strawberries, mustard greens, basil, lettuce, parsley, etc.

4. CONCLUSION

We have successfully manufactured an IoT device with acceptable accuracy to control nutrient concentration for aeroponic and hydroponic systems under greenhouse conditions. The IoT device has been successfully tested in the greenhouse and has the following functions: the greenhouse

- The system can automatically turn on the pump to provide more nutrients when it is below the threshold and turn off when the concentration has reached the threshold

- Users can directly enter the TDS threshold value in the field using the matrix keypad via the Blynk smartphone application.

The TDS sensor has a low measuring range. Therefore, the product can be applied to aeroponic and hydroponic systems with many types of plants, it is necessary to improve the nutrient concentration measurement range of this sensor.

THIẾT KẾ THIẾT BỊ KIỂM SOÁT TỰ ĐỘNG TỔNG NỒNG ĐỘ CHẤT RẮN HÒA TAN CỦA CHẤT DINH DƯỠNG CHO CÂY TRỒNG TRÊN HỆ KHÍ CANH, THỦY CANH

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Ngày nhận bài: 07/9/2022; Ngày phản biện thông qua: 20/10/2022; Ngày duyệt đăng: 21/10/2022

TÓM TẮT

Kiểm soát tổng nồng độ chất rắn hòa tan (Total Dissolved Solids, TDS) trong hệ thống khí canh và thủy canh rất quan trọng đối với sự phát triển của cây trồng. Do sự hồi lưu của dung dịch dinh dưỡng sau khi đi qua hệ thống ống chứa giá thể nên nồng độ các chất dinh dưỡng giảm dần. Hiện nay, việc đo nồng độ chất dinh dưỡng và bổ sung chất dinh dưỡng vào dung dịch được thực hiện thủ công bởi người nông dân. Do đó, chúng tôi đã sản xuất một thiết bị IoT (Internet of Things) với độ chính xác chấp nhận được để kiểm soát nồng độ chất dinh dưỡng. Trong thử nghiệm, cảm biến TDS có sai số tương đối ~ 1,2%. Thiết bị IoT có thể tự động bật máy bơm để cung cấp thêm chất dinh dưỡng khi TDS của nó dưới ngưỡng TDS và tắt máy bơm khi nồng độ đã đạt đến ngưỡng. Với hệ thống của chúng tôi, người dùng có thể nhập trực tiếp ngưỡng TDS bằng bàn phím ma trận hoặc thông qua ứng dụng điện thoại thông minh Blynk.

Từ khóa: IoT, nồng độ chất dinh dưỡng, hệ thống thủy canh và khí canh, TDS.

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